

Original software publication

Synthetic dataset generation system for vehicle detection

Mihaela Orić^{a,1,*}, Vlatko Galić^{a,b}, Filip Novoselnik^{a,c,1}

^a Protostar Labs, HR31551 Belišće, Croatia

^b Agricultural Institute Osijek, Osijek, Croatia

^c Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Computer Science and Information Technology Osijek, Osijek, Croatia

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

3D modeling
Synthetic data
Computer vision
Blender
Car detection
Machine learning

ABSTRACT

The success of machine learning models for object detection highly depends on the training data size and quality. Generating synthetic data speeds up the data acquisition process by removing the need for human annotation. Moreover, since annotation is done automatically, there is no room for human error. We present a pipeline that automatically generates and annotates aerial images of vehicles on roads. The pipeline is structured to allow easy adding of various new vehicles and is not limited to cars only. The resolution of the generated images and the level of detail can be modified by changing the output settings.

Code metadata

Current code version
Permanent link to code/repository used for this code version
Permanent link to reproducible capsule
Legal code license
Code versioning system used
Software code languages, tools and services used
Compilation requirements, operating environments and dependencies
If available, link to developer documentation/manual
Support email for questions

v1
<https://github.com/SoftwareImpacts/SIMPAC-2024-292>
<https://codeocean.com/capsule/2608662/tree/v1>
GNU GPLv3
git
Python, Blender
GeoPandas, Numpy, Pandas, Shapely
https://github.com/ProtostarLabs/synthetic_car_dataset_for_vehicle_detection/blob/main/README.md
mihaela.oric@protostar.ai

1. Introduction

Using machine learning for object detection has been proven to be a good approach. However, training a model that successfully detects objects in all cases requires a dataset of high quality. While there are many publicly available datasets for object detection, sometimes the use case is so specific that no available datasets fit the training needs. The solution to this problem is to create a dataset yourself [1], but that can be a resource-consuming task. Privacy issues present a problem when the images being collected contain personal information. Moreover, annotating images is a time-consuming task. Generating synthetic datasets overcomes both of those challenges. Furthermore,

when the annotation process is done automatically while data is being generated, the precision of annotations is perfect, and there is no human error factor, which is important because the quality of the annotations affects the training process significantly. There are publicly available datasets for car detection, a popular object detection task, but such datasets do not cover a specific use case that is car detection on aerial imagery. This motivated us to create a pipeline that serves the purpose of easy creation of annotated aerial images with different kinds of vehicles on roads. The pipeline is structured in a way that provides the user the ability to modify the height at which the aerial images are captured and their resolution, which replicates different use cases of car detection from the air, whether those images are taken using a UAV or satellites.

DOI of original article: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2024.110105>.

The code (and data) in this article has been certified as Reproducible by Code Ocean: (<https://codeocean.com/>). More information on the Reproducibility Badge Initiative is available at <https://www.elsevier.com/physical-sciences-and-engineering/computer-science/journals>.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: mihaela.oric@protostar.ai (M. Orić), vlatko.galic@protostar.ai (V. Galić), filip@protostar.ai (F. Novoselnik).

¹ Authors Mihaela Orić and Filip Novoselnik contributed equally.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.simpa.2024.100735>

Received 4 December 2024; Accepted 23 December 2024

Image 1. Software pipeline scheme.

2. Software description

3D modeling software Blender was used as the baseline for this framework due to its numerous advantages [2]. Some of those advantages are Blender's availability to everyone — it is free and open-source, and has an embedded Python interpreter which means that everything can be automated and all modeling and rendering steps can be done programmatically. Image 1 gives a visual explanation of the steps listed and described below.

Since the images represent aerial images captured with a nadir camera, the whole scene is a top-down view of some area, which is equivalent to a map. This means that the scenes can be recreated by using the available map service such as Google Maps. The Blender add-on BlenderGis allows importing maps and surface information and in this pipeline, it serves the purpose of loading base maps that serve as scenes [3]. Roads are loaded alongside the maps using BlenderGis and they are shaped as a mesh, or in other words, have vertices connected with edges. Each imported map is georeferenced and this georeference is used to set the position of the Sun in Blender. By adjusting the Sun position accordingly, 3D objects added to the scene will cast a shadow with the same angle and length as shadows visible on the map. For this feature to work properly, "Lighting: Sun Position" add-on should be enabled in Blender. To avoid having any vehicles visible on the map itself, each map has to be manually preselected by searching for areas without cars. When such an area is found, that scene is saved as a Blender file and can be loaded into the pipeline. We have preselected 10

different areas with varying scenery, such as villages, suburban areas, islands, highways, etc. However, users of this pipeline can select areas that fit their specific needs.

The models of vehicles preselected for this pipeline cover a wide range of personal cars [4], but users can also select specific vehicles and replace these car models with 3D models of their choice, keeping in mind that the scale of the models must represent the real-world size of those vehicles. The number of vehicles that will be added to the scene is set in the config file of this pipeline. Each vehicle is imported into the scene, and its location and rotation are modified. To avoid having cars placed randomly on any part of the scene, which would not be realistic since most cars are found on roads, the car models are placed on a random part of any road in the scene. This is done by selecting a random edge of the road and then a random point on that edge. The first step is to calculate the equation of the randomly selected edge. The x-value of the random point is selected by choosing a random value between the x-values of the starting and ending points of the selected edge. Finally, the y-value is calculated using the selected x-value and the edge equation. The angle of the edge, which is calculated from the edge equation, gives us the angle of the car, as cars are most often going in the direction of the road and are not perpendicular to it. The angle of the car can also be in the opposite direction which is easily calculated. After positioning the cars on the scene, their color is changed.

The next step is rendering the images. The camera locations are chosen randomly. Even though the map itself contains 2D data about the scene, it is loaded as a 3D object into the scene. To avoid the

Image 2. Generated scene with car colors variations.

Image 3. Generated scene with different shadows.

map being affected by the lighting of the scene in Blender and to keep the texture of the map from changing in Blender, all images had to be rendered in two parts. Firstly, the scene is rendered with the map having an emission shader without any shadows on the scene. Secondly, the scene is rendered without the emission shader with cars casting shadows on the map. The Blender Compositor is used to merge these two renders into the final rendered image. Since the map has its fixed resolution, a blur effect is added to the vehicles in the renders. Without this, the vehicles on the rendered images would stand out from the background and look unnatural.

The final part of this data generation pipeline is creating the annotations. Two of the most popular bounding box annotation formats were chosen, COCO bounding boxes written to a single json file and YOLO bounding boxes written to separate text files for each image. The calculations of the bounding boxes are done by transforming the 3D bounding boxes of objects in the scene into the 2D camera space. Image 2 shows examples of the images generated using this pipeline when the cars colors vary. Image 3 shows how the Sun position can be used to create different shadows.

3. Impact overview

“Synthetic Car Dataset” was created using this pipeline and is published to allow users to train vehicle detection models for aerial and satellite imagery [1]. Such models can be employed for various civil or government purposes, such as traffic detection and analysis, as well as surveillance. The size of the dataset created using this pipeline is not limited and can be large-scale, which would enable the training of deep learning models. Not only does this pipeline offer the user the ability to create large datasets, datasets created will also be of high quality, as the rendered images are close replicas of real photography.

This pipeline uses one of the most popular 3D modeling software, Blender, and the wide range of Blender users will find the greatest value of this work to be the automation of common Blender workflow steps. Even though it is made for generating annotated aerial vehicle images, the main steps – scene loading, object of interest loading, rendering, and extracting object bounding box information – can be applied for various different use cases. This work can serve as the starting point and guide for any software developer or 3D artist who wants to create their own training data.

4. Limitations and potential improvements

The number of vehicle models used in this work is relatively small, and adding different kinds of new vehicle 3D models would increase the variability of the datasets created using this pipeline, thus also expanding its envisioned usability. The resolution of the generated images is limited to a relatively low resolution of the map imported using BlenderGis. By using a different map service, or importing a custom-made maps, higher resolutions could be achieved, which would increase the quality of the datasets.

It is important to note that these limitations can be overcome by changing the assets used by the pipeline per se.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Mihaela Orić: Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.
Vlatko Galić: Methodology, Supervision, Writing – original draft.
Filip Novoselnik: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This research is supported by European Union's Horizon Europe research program Widening participation and spreading excellence, through project Strengthening Research and Innovation Excellence in

Autonomous Aerial Systems (AeroSTREAM) - Grant agreement ID: 101071270.

References

- [1] Mihaela Orić, et al., Synthetic car dataset for vehicle detection: Integrating aerial and satellite imagery, Data Brief 53 (2024) 110105, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2024.110105>.
- [2] <https://www.blender.org/>. (Accessed December 2023).
- [3] <https://github.com/domlysz/BlenderGIS>. (Accessed December 2023).
- [4] <https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/generic-passenger-car-pack-20f9af9b8a404d5cb022ac6fe87f21f5>. (Accessed December 2023).